

EUROPEAN COOPERATION
IN SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY

CA15104 TD(20)12045
Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium
January 27-29, 2020

EURO-COST

SOURCE: Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC)
Castelldefels, Spain.

Beam Selection for Hybrid Beamforming with Multi-Path Propagation: Novel Learning Architectures and Sufficient Statistics

Carles Antón-Haro (CTTC/iCERCA), Xavier Mestre (CTTC/iCERCA)

Carles Antón-Haro
Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia (PMT) – Building B6
Carl Frierich Gauss, 7
08860 Castelldefels (SPAIN)
Phone: + 34-93-645.29.00
Fax: + 34-93-645.29.01
Email: carles.anton@cttc.es

Beam Selection for Hybrid Beamforming with Multi-Path Propagation: Novel Learning Architectures and Sufficient Statistics

Carles Antón-Haro and Xavier Mestre

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia (PMT). Av Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, Building B6
08860 Castelfelers (SPAIN)
{carles.anton,xavier.mestre}@cttc.es

Abstract—In this paper, we investigate the applicability of deep and machine learning (ML/DL) techniques to beam selection problems. Specifically, we adopt a hybrid beamforming architecture comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) network followed by a zero-forcing (ZF) baseband processing block. The goal is to select the element in the ABF codebook yielding the highest sum-rate. The multi-antenna system operates in 5G NR's Frequency Range 2 and, accordingly, the ML/DL-based architecture has been designed to explicitly consider a number of practical aspects of such mmWave communication systems. In particular, the presence of multi-path propagation along with the use of multi-carrier signals precludes the use of (single) angle-of-arrival information as an input to the learning system. Therefore, we investigate here alternative sufficient statistics (SS) such as the singular vector/values of the (multi-carrier) channel matrix, the average covariance matrix, or the covariance matrix at a given subcarrier. Besides, the novel ML/DL architecture enables a continuous operation of the system and avoids the spectral efficiency losses associated to periodically switching to a dedicated ABF for SS estimation. Computer simulation results illustrate the performance of several ML/DL approaches (k-nearest neighbors, support vector classifiers, multi-layer perceptron) in realistic 5G scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) techniques have been known for a long time as powerful tools for classification and regression (prediction) problems. More recently, deep learning (DL) has emerged with more advanced tools capable of building universal classifiers and/or approximate general functions.

Over the last two decades, the application of ML/DL techniques to communication problems has been to a large extent confined to the field of wireless *network optimization* [1]. Consequently, there exists a large body of literature devoted to problems like intelligent resource management, cell association, selection of radio access technologies, or spectrum management, to name a few. More recently, the interest in using ML/DL techniques for problems and functionalities related with the physical layer (PHY) of communication systems

This work is partly supported by the European Commission through the Inclusive Radio Communications (IRACON) COST action, and the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities through the Statistical Learning and Inference for Large Dimensional Communication Systems (ARISTIDES, RTI2018-099722-B-I00) project

(e.g., coding, modulation, detection, equalization, pre-coding, among others) has dramatically increased. And, further, it is generally agreed that enhancing (or even replacing) some PHY functionalities with ML and DL approaches could help achieve the stringent requirements associated with the future releases of 5G [2]. For this reason, authors in [3] have started investigating how autoencoders can be used to model an end-to-end communication system comprising the encoding, channel and decoding blocks, for MIMO point-to-point and interference channels. The adoption of feedforward deep neural networks for joint channel estimation and data detection under an MMSE criterion is addressed in [4]. Other research works include the adoption of convolutional neural networks (CNN) to carry out sensing, compression and recovery of channel state information (CSI) in the feedback channel of massive MIMO systems [5]; the use of support vector classifiers (SVC) to perform antenna [6] or beam selection [7], or the exploitation of CNNs for modulation classification tasks [3].

The shift towards communications in mmWave bands makes it feasible to implement transceivers with many more antenna elements. In order to keep hardware cost and computational complexity at reasonable levels, a number of techniques have been proposed. Hybrid beamforming, for instance, can be used to partition beamforming into the digital and analog (RF) domains and, by doing so, reduce the number of *complete* (i.e., equipped with analog to digital converters) RF chains needed in the base station. In this context, the development of efficient (analog) beam selection techniques has become a hot research area. In [8], for instance, the authors present an iterative scheme where, in each iteration, the beam that contributes less to the sum-rate of a multi-user MIMO system with a discrete lens array and zero-forcing digital pre-coding block is eliminated. In [9], instead, the proposed low-complexity beam selection algorithm exploits the fact that an approximation of the sum-rate can be computed out of the elements of the effective channel matrix at the output of the analog beamforming (ABF) block. The approximation is near optimal in the high-SNR regime. A different approach is adopted in [10], where beam selection is accomplished with a bio-inspired ant colony optimization algorithm of a very reduced complexity.

The applicability of ML techniques to beam selection tasks is investigated in [7]. Specifically, the authors model beam selection (in a hybrid receiver architecture with a ZF block) as an instance of a multi-class classification problem, and attempt to solve it with a support vector classifier (SVC). To that aim, the availability of the actual angle-of-arrival (AoA) and amplitude information for each scattering path is assumed. Complementarily, in [11] Heath *et al* investigate the performance of several ML schemes (SVC, Adaboost, Decision trees, Random forests) but also deep neural networks (DNN) and reinforcement learning for beam pair selection in vehicle-to-infrastructure settings. The proposed method leverages on positioning information (vehicle locations) which is assumed to be supplied by an external entity and be error-free.

In this paper, we investigate the applicability of deep and machine learning-based methods (ML/DL) for analog beam selection in the uplink of a multi-user MIMO mmWave communication system. As in [7], [8], [10], we adopt a hybrid beamforming architecture comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) network plus a ZF baseband (digital) beamforming block (BBF). Specifically, we resort to support vector classifiers (like in [7], [11]) but also consider other schemes like k-nearest neighbors (that was used in [6] for transmit antenna selection) and the multi-layer perceptron (MLP). The rationale behind this choice is the different degrees of complexity/sophistication exhibited by those three schemes. In this context, we propose novel sufficient statistics to be used by the aforementioned ML/DL schemes based on (i) the singular value decomposition of the multi-carrier channel matrix; (ii) the covariance matrix averaged over subcarriers; or (iii) the covariance matrix of a given subcarrier. This is motivated by the fact that, as we discuss in this paper, in multi-carrier system scenarios with multi-path propagation, angle-of-arrival information cannot be used as a sufficient statistic. This approach is, thus, in stark contrast with and generalizes that of our previous work [16]. Besides, we also propose advanced learning system architectures with multiple learning blocks (instead of only one as the vast majority of authors do) that are needed to leverage the newly defined sufficient statistics. This learning architecture enables a continuous operation of the system since periodically switching to a dedicated beamformer for the estimation of the sufficient statistic (and the spectral efficiency losses that this entails) is not needed anymore.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the uplink of a multi-user SIMO system operating in the mmWave band. As shown in Fig. 1, the base station (BS) is equipped with N_{BS} antennas and serves K mobile terminals (or user equipments, UE). The BS adopts a hybrid beamforming architecture, comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) and a digital/baseband (BBF) beamforming block. The former performs a spatial pre-filtering of the received signal, whereas the latter is aimed at removing inter-user interference. The ABF network provides full connectivity among the set of receive antennas and the N_{RF} radiofrequency chains. Hereinafter, we assume that the number of active users does not

exceed the number of available RF chains (i.e., $K \leq N_{RF}$). In

Fig. 1: System Model.

an OFDM system, the received signal for the i -th subcarrier ($i = 1 \dots I$) after RF and baseband combining at the BS reads

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{W}_i^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{W}_i^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n}_i; \quad i = 1 \dots I \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times K}$ is the channel matrix, $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ denotes the transmit signal, with its elements fulfilling $\mathbb{E}[\|x_{k,i}\|^2] = P_i^t$ for $k = 1 \dots K$; vector $\mathbf{n}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times 1}$ is zero-mean i.i.d. AWGN noise with variance σ^2 , i.e., $\mathbf{n}_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_{BS}})$; and, finally, $\mathbf{W}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times K}$ and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times N_{RF}}$ stand for the BBF and ABF matrices, respectively. It should be noted that in equation (1) all the elements are defined on a per-subcarrier basis except for the *analog* beamforming matrix (ABF) that is shared by all subcarriers. This in turn implies that, even if the hybrid beamforming block is designed at the subcarrier level, the selection of the *analog* beamformer is carried out for the *entire* transmission band (i.e, not on a per-subcarrier basis). As for the channel, we adopt a geometric model with L_p scattering paths which is widely-used in mmWave communications. Consequently, for each of the columns of the channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_i = [\mathbf{h}_{1,i} \dots \mathbf{h}_{K,i}]$, we have that

$$\mathbf{h}_{k,i} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L_p \rho_k}} \sum_{p=1}^{L_p} \alpha_{k,p} e^{-j2\pi f_i \tau_{k,p}} \mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,p}^{BS}), \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_{k,p}$ and $\tau_{k,p}$ are the complex gain (with $\mathbb{E}[\|\alpha_{k,p}\|] = 1$) and the delay of the p -th path, respectively; f_i stands for the frequency of the i -th subcarrier, ρ_k accounts for path-loss and shadow fading between the BS and the k -th user, and $\theta_{k,p}^{BS}$ denotes the AoA of the p -th path of user k . Vector $\mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,p}^{BS})$ is the antenna array response at the BS. Hereinafter, we assume uniform linear arrays (ULA) and, hence, the $N_{BS} \times 1$ vector can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,p}^{BS}) = \left[1, e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin(\theta_{k,p}^{BS})}, \dots, e^{-j(N_{BS}-1)\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin(\theta_{k,p}^{BS})} \right] \quad (3)$$

where λ is the signal wavelength, and d is the distance between antenna elements (in the sequel, we assume $d = 0.5\lambda$). Throughout this work, the term SNR stands for the per-antenna signal-to-noise ratio.

A. Overview of 5G-NR's numerology

According to 5G-NR's numerology [17], the subcarrier spacing for data transmission in Frequency Range 2 (i.e. mmWave band, typically around 28 GHz) can take the values $\Delta f \in 60, 120$ kHz (with $f_i = f_0 + i \cdot \Delta f$). The maximum bandwidth for each component carrier (CC) is 200 MHz (for $\Delta f = 60$ kHz) or 400 MHz (for $\Delta f = 120$ kHz)¹. And, hence, the maximum number of subcarriers per CC is $I = 3300$. Resource elements are grouped into Physical Resource Blocks (PRB), each comprising 12 subcarriers.

For frequency spectrum above 6 GHz, 3GPP specifies a number of outdoor channel models, namely, urban microcell (UMi), urban macrocell (UMa), and rural macrocell (RMA). Each of those test models is parameterized with different values of e.g., path-loss exponent, standard deviation of the shadow fading, number of scattering paths and clusters, delays etc. For each environment, a number of scenarios are proposed (e.g., UMi-Street Canyon, UMi-Open Square). The interested reader is referred to [18], for further details.

III. ANALOG AND DIGITAL BEAMFORMING STRATEGIES

The proposed hybrid beamforming architecture for the BS comprises an analog and baseband (digital) beamforming blocks that are described in this section.

A. Analog Beamforming (ABF)

Let \mathcal{B} denote a pre-defined codebook of $B = |\mathcal{B}|$ different configurations² of the ABF network (referred to, in the sequel, as *analog beamformers*), namely,

$$\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{B}_1, \dots, \mathbf{B}_{|\mathcal{B}|}\} \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{B}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{BS}} \times N_{\text{RF}}}$ denoting each of those analog beamformers. Since we are interested in performing a spatial pre-filtering, we let the j -th column vector $\mathbf{b}_{i,j}$ in $\mathbf{B}_i = [\mathbf{b}_{i,1}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{i,N_{\text{RF}}}]$ point at a different direction θ_d out of a set of D AoAs evenly spaced in $[-\pi/2 \dots \pi/2]$. And, as a design decision, we set D in such a way that the resulting number of elements (analog beamformers) in the codebook $B = \binom{D}{N_{\text{RF}}}$ is larger than or equal to N_{BS} .

A straightforward choice for $\mathbf{b}_{i,j} = \mathbf{b}_{i,j}(\theta_d)$ would be phased arrays, namely,

$$\mathbf{s}(\theta_d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{\text{BS}}}} \left[1, e^{j\pi \sin(\theta_d)}, \dots, e^{j(N_{\text{BS}}-1)\pi \sin(\theta_d)} \right] \quad (5)$$

For large N_{BS} , however, the resulting beams become too narrow (to recall, their 3 dB beamwidth is $2/N_{\text{BS}}$). However, as discussed in [16], this yields a poor classification performance (i.e., accuracy in ABF selection) and, thus, must be avoided. Instead, we let \mathbf{b} (sub-indices i, j have been dropped, for brevity) be the solution to the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{b}}{\text{maximize}} && \int_{\theta_d - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_d + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}} \mathbf{b}^H \mathbf{s}(\theta) \mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{b} \, d\theta \\ & \text{subject to} && \|\mathbf{b}\|^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

¹Larger bandwidths can be achieved via carrier aggregation (up to 16 CCs).

²To recall, each of those configurations is fixed for *all* the subcarriers of the component carrier, as discussed in Section II

where $\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}$ is a design parameter related with the interval around θ_d where we want to *broaden* the beam. In [16], we found that $\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}$ must be carefully designed since the performance of the ABF selection scheme critically depends on its choice.

Figure 2 below depicts the periodogram of the *set* of analog beamformers in a codebook designed according to (6). For illustrative purposes, we superimpose the AoAs of the various multi-path components with the spatial response (periodogram) of each beamformer. Clearly, beamformer #1 will exhibit a poor sum-rate performance since virtually all the multi-path components associated to the red user are canceled out.

Fig. 2: Periodograms of selected elements in the ABF codebook. Each color of the triangles corresponds to one user in the system. The power of each multi-path component is normalized to that of the strongest path for each user ($N_{\text{BS}} = 16$, $N_{\text{RF}} = 3$, $K = 2$, $\Delta\theta/ = 3/D$, $D = 8$).

B. Baseband Beamforming (BBF)

For baseband beamforming, we adopt a zero-forcing ZF scheme, as e.g., in [7]. The *effective* channel matrix for subcarrier i can be defined as the product of the actual channel in that subcarrier and the (common) analog beamforming matrix, namely, $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H}_i$. From this, we have that matrix \mathbf{W}_i in (1) reads:

$$\mathbf{W}_i = (\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i})^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}^H. \quad (7)$$

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Our goal is to select the analog beamformer from the B -element codebook \mathcal{B} such that the sum rate at the output of the BBF block is maximized. From the system model presented in the preceding section, the instantaneous sum rate can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} R(b) &= \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 (1 + \gamma_{k,i}(b)) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{k,i}^t}{\sigma^2 \left[(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}(b)^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}(b))^{-1} \right]_{kk}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_{k,i}$ is the SINR at the i -th subcarrier of user k , and $[\mathbf{A}]_{kk}$ denotes the k -th element in the diagonal of

matrix \mathbf{A} . Notice that, for clarity, the dependency of $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}$ on the codebook index b has been made explicit in the above expression.

Since the number of subcarriers in a 5G-NR component carrier is potentially very large (up to 3300 in FR2, see Section II) and the computation in each subcarrier requires one matrix inversion, some simplification in the calculation is advisable. Figure ?? depicts the rate for each individual user over the entire bandwidth of the CC. Clearly, the individual rates (as well as the resulting sum-rate) exhibit very smooth variations. Hence, there is no point in (re-)calculating the sum-rate for more than one subcarrier in each PRB (12 subcarriers). In some scenarios, an additional downsampling factor F_{ds} can be safely applied (see Section VII ahead).

Fig. 3: Individual rates and sum rates for each subcarrier. ($N_{\text{BS}} = 16$, $N_{\text{RF}} = 6$, $K = 4$, $\Delta\theta/ = 3/D$, $D = 8$, UMi test channel).

V. NEED FOR ALTERNATIVE SUFFICIENT STATISTICS AND LEARNING SYSTEM ARCHITECTURES

In order to select the optimal beamformer (and avoid an exhaustive search over the codebook elements), one should leverage on \mathbf{H}_i as channel state information (CSI). However, under the assumption of a hybrid beamforming architecture, \mathbf{H}_i cannot be readily estimated in the digital domain (since the number of RF chains, N_{RF} , is smaller than the number of antennas, N_{BS}). Alternatively, we propose to use some sufficient statistic (SS) derived from \mathbf{H}_i . In our previous work [16], we learnt that in single scattering path *and* single-carrier scenarios the AoA and received power information for each user turned out to be a sufficient statistic. In fact, this allowed us to model the beam selection problem as a classification one that, ultimately, could be solved via ML/DL methods.

Unfortunately, those assumptions do not hold anymore for the current work. Here, on the one hand, we consider a scenario with multiple and possibly correlated scattering paths. And, besides, the number of paths is assumed to be unknown (actually, it is a random variable). In these circumstances, the AoAs and receiver power estimators used in [16] (minimum variance, MULTIPLE SIGNAL CLASSIFICATION -MUSIC-) cannot be used. On the other, the combined effect of multi-path components in each subcarrier varies, since each scattering path experiences a different delay (see second term in equation (2)). In other words, the SSS of multi-carrier/OFDM signals

are (potentially) subcarrier-dependent. This implies a linear increase in the number of statistics to be estimated and then used by our learning system. And, in turn, the system must solve a more complex problem. To alleviate this, in the next subsection we propose alternative sufficient statistics suitable for multi-path and multi-carrier scenarios.

Besides, in [16] the ABF matrices used for the (i) AoA estimation phase; and (ii) data transmission phase in each frame were different. This is motivated by the fact that using the *directional* analog beamformer \mathbf{B} (see Section III-A), which was optimal for the *preceding* data frame, may result in a partial or total cancelation of the received signals in the *current* data frame. And, thus, the AoAs for the current data frame cannot be readily estimated. To circumvent that, a set of *non-directional* beamformers \mathbf{B}_b was used for AoA estimation only. Specifically, we let $\mathbf{B}_b = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{Q}^H\mathbf{Q})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where \mathbf{Q} is a $N_{\text{BS}} \times N_{\text{RF}}$ matrix of complex-valued random i.i.d. Gaussian entries. However, using the same ABF for both tasks is highly desirable since this allows to transmit data in both phases (i.e., reduction of signalling overhead). To achieve this, a novel architecture of the learning system is proposed in Section VI-B ahead.

A. Sufficient statistics - description

An obvious choice here would be to use as SS the set of effective channel matrices $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}$ $i = 1 \dots I$. In this case, however, the total number of parameters³ in the SS vector ($N_s = 2N_{\text{BS}}KI$) is much larger since it scales linearly in the number of subcarriers. This, of course, is barely recommended. As discussed in Section VI-A, the number of inputs to the learning scheme (ML or DL-based) equals the number of elements in the SS vector. Hence, the larger N_s , the higher the training complexity and, also, memory requirements.

In order to obtain more compact SSS, we propose three different strategies:

- 1) **Singular Value Decomposition of Effective Channel matrices** (SVDECh strategy): Let $\mathbf{h}_{\text{eff},k,i}$ denote the k -th column in the effective (filtered) channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff},i}$. Then we define $\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff},k} = [\mathbf{h}_{\text{eff},k,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{\text{eff},k,I}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RF}} \times I}$ which gathers the effective channel vectors of user k for all subcarriers. The singular value decomposition of such matrix reads⁴ $\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}} = \mathcal{U}_{\text{eff}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{eff}}\mathcal{V}_{\text{eff}}^H$, with \mathcal{U}_{eff} and \mathcal{V}_{eff} standing for orthonormal matrices, and \mathcal{L}_{eff} denoting a real-valued diagonal matrix. Clearly, the left singular vector in \mathcal{U}_{eff} associated to the largest singular value in \mathcal{L}_{eff} can be regarded as a spatial signature of user k . Specifically, this signature provides spatial information for the strongest multi-path component *averaged over subcarriers*. This avoids a linear scaling of the dimension of the SS vector in the number of subcarriers. Consequently, we have that $N_s = 2N_{\text{RF}}K + K$ where the last term in the summation corresponds to the largest

³Since channel matrices are complex-valued and ML/DL schemes typically operate with real-valued inputs, a multiplicative factor of 2 must be included.

⁴Subscript k is dropped here for the brevity of notation.

(real-valued) elements in the diagonal matrices \mathcal{L}_{eff} of each user.

- 2) **Average Effective Covariance Matrix** (AECv strategy): The signal at the output of the ABF block for subcarrier i reads $\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n}_i$; $i = 1 \dots I$. The covariance matrix for this signal is given by $\mathbf{R}_{y_i} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_i \mathbf{y}_i^H]$. Clearly, \mathbf{R}_{y_i} contains all the spatial information of the scenario as observed by subcarrier i . Therefore, its role as a SS deserves being explored, as well. Again, to avoid the linear scaling in the number of subcarriers, we take the ensemble average of the covariance matrices over subcarriers. In this case, the dimension of the (real-valued) SS vector is $N_s = N_{RF}^2 + N_{RF}$, where we have exploited the fact that \mathbf{R}_{y_i} is Hermitian and, thus, half of the off-diagonal elements can be dropped.
- 3) **Effective Covariance Matrix** (ECv strategy): Differently from the previous strategy, here we do not average covariance matrices. Instead, we just select the covariance matrix of a given subcarrier and use it as SS. This strategy will be mostly used as a benchmark: the lower the number of subcarriers, the more similar the performances of AECv and ECv will be. Of course, here we have again that $N_s = N_{RF}^2 + N_{RF}$.

VI. DATA-DRIVEN ANALOG BEAM SELECTION

The task of selecting the optimal analog beamformer can be modeled as a supervised learning problem. Specifically it can be cast into a multi-class classification task where:

- The input for the m -th example is given by the sufficient statistics (SS) associated to active users, namely, the row vector $\mathbf{t}_m = [t_{1,m}, \dots, t_{N_s,m}] \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N_s}$.
- The output is an index to the element (beamformer) in the codebook, $b_m \in [1, \dots, B]$, yielding the highest sum rate after ZF. Such an output avoids performing the costly matrix product and inversion in (9) for *every* analog beamformer in the codebook that an exhaustive search requires.

The next subsections describe (i) the training set to be used; (ii) the architecture of the learning system; and (iii) the specific machine and deep learning schemes considered in this work.

A. Training set description

The training set comprises a total of M examples \mathbf{t}_m stacked in a training matrix $\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{t}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{t}_M^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N_s}$ and a class label vector $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_M]^T \in \mathbb{N}^{M \times 1}$ that gathers the corresponding outputs (i.e., $c_m = b_m \forall m$). The generation of the training set comprises the following steps:

- 1) Generation the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario (user locations, transmit powers, path-loss).
- 2) Computation of the sufficient statistic chosen as per Section V-A.
- 3) Performing ABF and BBF on the received signal for each example and every analog beamformer in the codebook, as in (1).

- 4) Computation of the corresponding sum rates as per (9);
- 5) Letting the label of each example be the index of the analog beamformer yielding the highest sum rate, i.e., $\mathbf{c}_m \in \{1, 2, \dots, B\}$.

To avoid significant bias in the training, features are normalized prior to their use by the learning schemes, namely, $t_{ij} \leftarrow (t_{ij} - E_i t_{ij}) / (\max_i [t_{ij}] - \min_i [t_{ij}])$

B. Architecture of the learning system

It should be noted that the SSs proposed in Section V-A depend, in all cases, on the specific ABF in use. This stems from the fact that the SSs (SVD vectors, covariance matrices, etc) are computed *after* spatial filtering by the ABF block. In other words, channels, covariance matrices, etc are *effective* too, according to the previous definition. This is in stark contrast with the estimated AoA and received power SSs of [16] which were ABF-agnostic, since a *non-directional* ABF was used for their computation (see discussion in Section IV).

All this has a number of architectural implications on the learning system. Since SSs are ABF-specific, it seems reasonable to use a dedicated learning block (based on e.g., neural network, SVC, kNN algorithm,...) for the SSs generated with each ABF. By doing so, each learning block is specifically *tuned* to a different subset of SSs. In fact, a mismatch between the ABFs used in the training and test phases will result into a substantial performance degradation (see computer simulations section ahead). On the contrary, if we had a single learning block (as in [16]), it would be adjusted to some sort of average SS during the training phase. And, thus, a poorer performance could be expected in the test phase. Having multiple learning blocks running in parallel, though, comes at a price of (i) additional memory requirements; and (ii) an increase of the computational burden in the training phase (e.g., to compute and store the weights of each learning block).

The proposed architecture of the learning system is depicted in Figure 4, both for the training and test phases. Notably, we have as many learning blocks as ABFs in the codebook (B). As discussed above, the SSs used as an input to each learning block in the training phase (top) are ABF-specific. On the contrary, the output signal needed for the supervised learning process (i.e., the optimal ABF for each example m , b_m^*) is identical for all learning blocks (since, ultimately, it depends on the *non-filtered* channel matrices $\{\mathbf{H}_1, \dots, \mathbf{H}_I\}_m$). In the test phase (bottom), the received signal is first pre-filtered with the optimal ABF estimated in the *previous* data frame: $\mathbf{B}_{\hat{b}[n-1]}$, with $\hat{b}[n-1]$ denoting the corresponding codebook index. This index also determines the block to which the SS will be routed to, $\hat{b}[n-1]$, since this is the one that is more tuned to such filtered information. Finally, the selected learning block will be used to estimate the optimal ABF for the *current* data frame, namely, $\hat{b}[n]$.

C. Machine Learning Schemes

The so-called k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) scheme is one of the simplest ML-based classification methods. For a new

Fig. 4: Architecture of the learning system in the training (top) and test (bottom) phases.

example \mathbf{t} , the kNN classifier finds the k nearest⁵ entries in the training set \mathbf{T} . Then kNN declares the class label for the new example \mathbf{t} based on a (possibly weighted) majority of the nearest neighbors' labels. The only hyper-parameter of the algorithm is G , the number of nearest neighbors to find. Typically, G is set to be an odd number, to avoid ambiguity.

We also consider a Support Vector Classifier (SVC). For a multi-class classification problems (like ours), SVCs need to solve B binary classification problems. Each of them, identifies one category vs. the other categories (i.e. one-vs.-rest approach). Specifically, during the training phase, binary SVCs fit a separating hyperplane with optimal geometric margin (i.e. maximum distance to the closest elements in each of the two classes). Next, in the test phase, those hyperplanes are used to decide in which region (i.e., class, beamformer index) the new example \mathbf{t} lies⁶. Since our problem is not linearly separable (see Fig. 6), we introduce a Gaussian (radial-based) kernel function to transform the input data. This allows to transform hyperplanes into more general boundaries. For this kernel in particular, the hyperparameters are σ_k , the variance of the Gaussian kernel; and, C , a penalty parameter aimed to balance bias and overfitting (see [12] for details).

D. Deep Learning Scheme

Feedforward Deep Neural Networks (DNN) like the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) can be regarded as universal function

⁵In this work, we restrict ourselves to the most popular distance measure: the Euclidean distance, namely, $d(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{t}) = \|\mathbf{t}_m - \mathbf{t}\|^2$

⁶If binary SVCs predict multiple labels, the one with the highest confidence score is finally selected.

Fig. 5: Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), a feedforward deep neural network.

approximators. As shown in Fig. 5, our L -layer MLP consists of: one input layer with N_s elements (AoAs, received powers), one output layer with B neurons (the number of elements in the codebook), and $L - 2$ hidden layers with N_l ; $l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{N_s} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^B$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (9)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends, on the one hand, on the output of the previous layer and, on the other, on the parameter set of that layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model (see below for details). The l -th layer is said to be *dense* if $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l)$ is of the form

$$f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l) = \sigma(\mathbf{G}_l \mathbf{r}_{l-1} + \mathbf{u}_l) \quad (10)$$

with $\mathbf{G}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ and $\mathbf{u}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ denoting a matrix of weights and a bias vector, respectively; and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a (typically non-linear) activation function. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. On the contrary, a Softmax activation function is used at the output layer, so that the probability for each beamformer can be effectively computed. Further, each hidden layer is followed by a dropout layer in order to avoid overfitting when using the training set. In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer, i.e., $\phi_l = [\mathbf{G}_l, \mathbf{u}_l]$, is adjusted via the so-called stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [19]) and backpropagation [12]. The goal is to minimize the categorical cross entropy (i.e., maximize classification accuracy).

VII. PRELIMINARY PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we conduct a preliminary performance assessment of the proposed ML- and DL-based beam selection schemes. We consider a scenario with one gNodeB (gNB) equipped with $N_{BS} = 16$ receive antennas, $N_{RF} = 3$ RF chains, and a total of $K = 2$ active users with identical transmit power ($P_k = P = 30$ dBm). Out of the $B = 20$ elements in the codebook, we restrict ourselves to using only

$B_{\text{sub}} = 10$. This significantly reduces the computational complexity of the ML/DL algorithms with a marginal performance penalty (see [16] for details). As for the propagation channel, we adopt the standard Urban Micro (UMi) test model [18] under Line-of-Sight (LOS) conditions. The path-loss exponent is $n = 2$ and the standard deviation of the shadow fading is $\sigma_{SF} = 4$ dB. The gNB to UE distances are uniformly distributed in the range [10, 100] m, and the angular spread of the AoAs of the multi-path components is set to 10° (Laplacian distribution with, typically, $L_p \in [1, 10]$). As for modulation-related parameters, the total number of subcarriers is $I = 420$ with subcarrier spacing equal to $\Delta f = 120$ kHz. This yields a total RF bandwidth of roughly 50 MHz. The carrier frequency is 28 GHz. For the computation of sum-rates, we consider an additional down-sampling factor of $F_{\text{DS}} = 2$ (i.e., only one out of 24 subcarriers is used).

Computer simulation results are given in terms of classification accuracy and sum-rate. As benchmarks, we include (i) a *random* beam selection (uniform distribution in $\{1, \dots, B\}$); and (ii) an *optimal* beam selection, which is accomplished via exhaustive search.

A. Description of Simulation Tools

To generate the channel responses, we resorted to NYUSIM [20], a stochastic open-source mmWave channel simulator. NYUSIM is based on extensive field measurements from 28 GHz to 140 GHz, it can operate over a wide range of carrier frequencies (500 MHz - 100 GHz), and supports wide RF bandwidths of up to 800 MHz. Different types of antenna arrays are also supported, such as uniform linear array (ULA) or uniform rectangular array (URA) at the transmitter and the receiver.

For the implementation, training and evaluation of the proposed schemes, we resorted to the Scikit-learn [21] and Tensorflow [22] libraries, for ML (kNN, SVC) and DL (MLP) ones, respectively. Besides, we also used Keras [23], which runs on top of TensorFlow (and also other DL libraries like Theano or CNTK) and provides a high-level neural network API (Application Programming Interface) to it. Unless otherwise stated, the number of examples in the training and test sets was set to $M = 3000$ and $M_{\text{test}} = 3000$, respectively (details on the training set can be found in Section VI-A). As for tuning, the hyper-parameters in each model were optimized via grid search: $G = [3, 5, 10, 20, 50, 80, 100, 200]$, $\sigma_k = [10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 5]$, and $C = [1, 10, 100, 1000, 2000, 5000]$. To that aim, a cross-validation factor of 5 (i.e., 20% of the examples were reserved for testing) was considered, both for the kNN and SVC schemes. To recall, for the SVC we used a Radial Basis Function as a Kernel, and a 'one-over-the-rest' decision function (see Section VI-C). A different model was fit for each SNR. As for the MLP, the number of layers and neurons in the hidden layers was $L = 5$ and $N_l = 125$, respectively. During training, the dropout rate was set to 20% which sufficed to prevent overfitting. The total number of training iterations was set to 200. For the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad), the learning

rate was set to 0.01, and a batch size of 32 samples was used for the computation of the gradient (for further details on the configuration of the MLP scheme, please, see Section VI-D). All the aforementioned parameters were manually optimized.

B. Computer simulation results

First, we analyze the impact of channel propagation conditions on the actual decision regions of the classifier. The ultimate goal is to check the validity of using AoAs as a sufficient statistic (assuming they could be estimated). The scatterplot of Figure 6 shows which is the optimal beamformer as a function of the actual AoA of each user's strongest path. For scenarios with a single scattering path (left and center), the decision regions continue to be connected, as in [16]. When no power control mechanism is in place (i.e., in the presence of channel fluctuations), the received powers of the active users should also be included in the SS, since they are different now. Still, the decision regions for this case do not change significantly (center). This means that, as such, AoAs still manage to capture most of the information in the received signal⁷. On the contrary, in the presence of multi-path propagation (right) decision regions are not compact anymore (see circles of a different color penetrating other decision regions). Determining the boundaries between beamformer regions, the task that the classification algorithm is confronted with, becomes a much more difficult task. And, consequently, classification performance degrades. In fact, the larger the angular spread, the more noticeable this effect is. The same holds for scenarios where the channel response is substantially different over subcarriers (due e.g., to large delay spreads of the scattering paths and/or a high number of subcarriers). All this, along with the issues discussed in Section V, substantiates the need for exploring alternative SSs, like the ones proposed in Section V-A.

Next, we turn our attention to the impact of the receive SNR at the RF antennas on classification accuracy (Fig. 7). Results are shown for the different learning methods (kNN, SVC, and MLP), and sufficient statistics (SVDECh, AECv, and ECv). First, we observe that by using SVDECh as a SS accuracies of up to 60% can be achieved. Apparently, computing the SVD of the $\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff},k}$ matrices (and the additional complexity this brings about) helps identify the relevant spatial information. And, to recall, such a signature can be computed regardless of the number of scattering paths of the channel. On the contrary, all learning methods find difficulties in distilling the spatial information which is embedded in the covariance matrices \mathbf{R}_{y_i} themselves (at least for this scenario). As a result, classification accuracies are very low, on the order of 25%. Interestingly, the gains of the AECv vs. the ECv, when they exist, are rather marginal. As for the ML/DL methods, classification accuracy when using SVDECh as a SS clearly depends on algorithmic complexity: MLP outperforms SVC, and SVC outperforms kNN (their performance when using the

⁷This is despite of the fact that, for UMi channels, the received powers may differ significantly.

Fig. 6: Actual decision regions with (i) single-path and identical received power (left); (ii) single-path and different received powers (center); and (iii) multi-path and different received powers (left) ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $K = 2$, $SNR = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 20$, $B_{\text{sub}} = 10$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 6$, UMi channel model).

other two SSs experiences a substantial degradation, anyway). In general, DNNs turn out to be more sophisticated classifiers than *classical* ML ones, this allowing them to handle more complex decision regions (like the ones scenarios with multi-path propagation and fluctuations in the received powers) more efficiently. Besides, the impact of the SNR on classification performance is negligible. Apparently, the fact that ML/DL models are trained for specific SNRs largely mitigates such an impact. Finally, we also investigate the impact of a mismatch between the ABFs used in the training and test phases. Specifically, in the test phase, we continue to use the ABF from the previous data frame to compute the SS, but it is routed to an arbitrary learning block ($1, \dots, B$, see Fig. 4) which is selected randomly. When this happens, the classification accuracy drops to roughly one third of that obtained with the correct learning block (for all learning algorithms and SVDECh as a SS). This proves that the specificities of each ABF when it comes to generating SSs, were effectively embodied in each learning block during the training phase.

Yet classification accuracy is a relevant performance measure, from a communications point of view we are often more interested in sum rates. This is illustrated in Fig. 8. Very interestingly, the sum-rate of the MLP approach is very close to that of optimal beam selection. And this happens despite of the fact that its classification accuracy is approximately 60% (see Fig. 7 above). This is due to the fact, specially in the presence of multiple propagation paths, more than one ABF in the codebook is able to detect a given active user (and mitigate others) via such paths. Consequently, their sum-rates are similar. This effect can be readily observed in Fig. 2 of Section III-A. When classification accuracy degrades further, for instance for the kNN and SVC approaches, the sum-rate loss become more noticeable. Nevertheless, for this particular scenario, these two ML schemes still manage to retain some 95% of the achievable sum-rate with optimal beam selection. Again, the fact that the DL approach (MLP) outperforms its

Fig. 7: Classification accuracy for different learning methods and sufficient statistics ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $K = 2$, $SNR = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 20$, $B_{\text{sub}} = 10$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 6$, UMi channel model).

ML counterparts (kNN, SVC) comes at a price of a higher computational complexity of this classification tool. A more detailed complexity analysis is left for subsequent works.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have investigated how a number of learning-based approaches can be used to perform beam selection in a hybrid beamforming setup. Specifically, we have posed beam selection as a multi-class classification problem and solved it via two machine-learning approaches: k-nearest neighbors (kNN), support vector classifiers (SVC); and one deep learning approach: the multilayer perceptron (MLP). In this context, we have proposed (i) novel sufficient statistics based on the singular value decomposition of the multi-carrier

Fig. 8: Percentage of the sum-rate vs. signal-to-noise ratio ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $K = 2$, $SNR = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 20$, $B_{\text{sub}} = 10$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 6$, UMi channel model, SVDECh strategy).

channel matrix (SVDECh), the covariance matrix averaged over subcarriers (AECv) or the covariance matrix of a given subcarrier (ECv); and (ii) advanced learning system architectures with multiple learning blocks, suitable for multi-carrier signals in multi-path propagation scenarios. Besides, the novel learning architecture enables a continuous operation of the system and avoids the spectral efficiency losses associated to periodically switching beamformers between the SS estimation and data transmission phases of a data frame. Performance evaluation has been accomplished via computer simulations in realistic 5G-NR scenarios. Preliminary results indicate that using SVDECh as a sufficient statistics achieves a higher classification accuracy, on the order of 60%, than AECv or ECv. And that, in general, MLP outperforms both kNN and SVC methods in terms of classification accuracy. As a result, its sum-rate is very close to that of optimal beam selection. As for the ML schemes, they retain some 95% of the sum-rate with optimal beam selection. This study should be regarded as work in progress. Future work in this area includes, inter-alia, a more comprehensive performance assessment (e.g, with a larger number of users, other test channels), and the use of e.g, reinforcement learning approaches to avoid re-training of the learning system when channel conditions vary.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Jiang, H. Zhang, Y. Ren, Z. Han, K. C. Chen, and L. Hanzo, "Machine learning paradigms for next-generation wireless networks," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 98–105, April 2017.
- [2] ITU, "IMT Vision – framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2020 and beyond," *International Telecommunication Union (ITU), Recommendation ITU-R M.2083-0*, Sep. 2015.
- [3] T. O’Shea and J. Hoydis, "An introduction to deep learning for the physical layer," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 563–575, Dec 2017.
- [4] H. Ye, G. Y. Li, and B. H. Juang, "Power of deep learning for channel estimation and signal detection in OFDM systems," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 114–117, Feb 2018.

- [5] C. Wen, W. Shih, and S. Jin, "Deep learning for massive MIMO CSI feedback," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1–1, Oct. 2018.
- [6] J. Joung, "Machine learning-based antenna selection in wireless communications," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 20, no. 11, pp. 2241–2244, Nov 2016.
- [7] Y. Long, Z. Chen, J. Fang, and C. Tellambura, "Data-driven based analog beam selection for hybrid beamforming under mm-wave channels," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1–1, May 2018.
- [8] R. Pal, K. V. Srinivas, and A. K. Chaitanya, "A beam selection algorithm for millimeter-wave multi-user MIMO systems," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 852–855, April 2018.
- [9] Y. Niu, Z. Feng, Y. Li, Z. Zhong, and D. Wu, "Low complexity and near-optimal beam selection for millimeter wave MIMO systems," in *2017 13th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC)*, June 2017, pp. 634–639.
- [10] S. Qiu, K. Luo, and T. Jiang, "Beam selection for mmwave massive MIMO systems under hybrid transceiver architecture," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 227, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [11] A. Klautau, P. Batista, N. Gonzalez-Prelcic, Y. Wang, and R. Heath, "5G MIMO data for machine learning: Application to beam selection using deep learning," in *Proceedings of the Information Theory and Applications Workshop 2018*, Feb. 2018.
- [12] A. Smola and S. Vishwanathan, *Introduction to Machine Learning*, 2008.
- [13] D. He, C. Liu, T. Q. S. Quek, and H. Wang, "Transmit antenna selection in MIMO wiretap channels: A machine learning approach," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 634–637, 2018.
- [14] A. Mukherjee and A. Hottinen, "Learning algorithms for energy-efficient mimo antenna subset selection: Multi-armed bandit framework," in *2012 Proceedings of the 20th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, Aug 2012, pp. 659–663.
- [15] H. L. V. Trees, *Optimum Array Processing: Part IV of Detection, Estimation, and Modulation Theory*. John Wiley & Sons Inc., 2002.
- [16] C. Antón-Haro and X. Mestre, "Data-driven beam selection for mmwave communications with machine and deep learning: an angle of arrival-based approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, p. 20404 – 20415, Jan. 2019.
- [17] "NR: Physical channels and modulation," 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Tech. Rep. TS 138 211 V15.2.0, December 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://www.3gpp.org/DynaReport/38211.htm>
- [18] "Study on channel model for frequency spectrum above 6 GHz," 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Tech. Rep. TR 38.900 v14.2.0, July 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.3gpp.org/DynaReport/38900.htm>
- [19] J. Duchi, E. Hazan, and Y. Singer, "Adaptive subgradient methods for online learning and stochastic optimization," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, p. 2121–2159, 2011.
- [20] New York University and NYU Wireless Group. (2016–2019) NYUSIM - NYU wireless simulator. [Online]. Available: <https://wireless.engineering.nyu.edu/nyusim/>
- [21] "Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python," <https://scikit-learn.org>, note = Accessed: 2018-09-20.
- [22] "Tensorflow: An open source machine learning library for research and production," <https://www.tensorflow.org>, note = Accessed: 2018-09-20.
- [23] "Keras: The python deep learning library," <https://keras.io/>, note = Accessed: 2018-09-20.